

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotatsiya: This article covers the concept of pedagogical technology, the history of the development of pedagogical eras and technologies, the development of pedagogical technologies in the XXth century, and centers of pedagogical technology in developed countries.

Kalit soʻzlar: interactive, non-traditional methods, pedagogical technologies, methods of activity, cooperation, efficiency, guidance, competence, skills, assessment criteria.

Today, a number of developed countries are gaining significant experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process.

Understanding pedagogical technology

Scientific and technical progress by the end of the XXth century not only led to the technologization of many production sectors, but also penetrated the sphere of culture and the humanitarian fields of knowledge. Pedagogical technology is usually understood as a direction in pedagogy aimed at increasing the efficiency of the educational process and achieving the desired results in education (M. Klarin, 1989).

The term “pedagogical technology” is an imprecise translation of the English phrase “an educational technology”. The concept of “pedagogical technology” has recently been used more widely in the theory of education. More than 300 definitions have been given in the pedagogical literature to the term “technology” and its forms

such as “educational technology”, “educational technology”, “technology in education”. The term “pedagogical technology” was first mentioned in works on pedagogy in the 1920s. Currently, the concept of pedagogical technology has various expressions.

1. Technology is a set of methods used in a particular work, skill, art (explanatory dictionary).

2. Pedagogical technology is a technique for implementing the educational process (V.P. Bespalko).

3. Pedagogical technology is a description of the process of achieving planned results in teaching (I.P. Volkov).

4. Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical instructions that determine the structure and specific set of educational tools, forms, methods, methods, techniques, that is, an organizational and methodological tool of the pedagogical process (B.T. Likhachev).

5. Pedagogical technology is a systematic approach to the creation, application and definition of the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human capabilities and their interrelationships, which poses the problem of optimizing forms of education (UNESCO).

6. Technology is an art, skill, skill, a set of development methods, a change in the state (V.M. Shepel).

7. Educational technology is a comprehensively thought-out model of collaborative pedagogical activity for designing, organizing and conducting the educational process in order to create absolutely comfortable conditions for students and teachers (V.M. Monakhov).

8. Pedagogical technology is a systematic way of thinking in pedagogy (T. Sakamoto).

9. Pedagogical technology is a system of development that changes the organizational form, methods, and content of the educational process (E. Bistereki and J. Seller).

10. Pedagogical technology is a systematic collection and order of use of all personal, instrumental, and methodological means used to achieve pedagogical goals (M.V. Klarin).

11. Pedagogical technology is a systematic, conceptual, regular, objectified, invariant description of the activities of the teacher and student aimed at achieving the goal of education (F.A. Fradkin).

12. Educational technology is a comprehensive, integrated process that includes the methods of organizing activities, people, ideas, and tools for planning, managing, and analyzing the provision of knowledge (American Association for Educational Communications and Technology).

History of pedagogical eras and the development of technologies

The history of pedagogy shows that the search for more perfect methods and techniques of teaching and training personnel has been ongoing. Teaching is a productive activity, like any other activity, although its effect on the development of society may not be immediately apparent upon completion of the teacher's work.

Economic periods in the history of society do not differ only in what is produced, how much is produced by whom, and with what means of labor.

From this perspective, if we look at the "pedagogical eras" that have existed in social history:

I. The era of the pedagogical activity of the individual teacher, the manual teacher (from ancient times to the 17th century);

II. The era of the notebook (from the 17th century to the present);

III. The era of audiovisual tools (the 50s of the 20th century).

IV. The era of simple tools for automating educational management (the 70s of the 20th century).

V. The era of adaptive tools for automating educational management based on modern computers (computer-based education at the end of the 20th century).

The development of pedagogical technologies in the XXth century as a pedagogical technological development

By the end of the 20th century, scientific and technical progress not only led to the technologization of production, but also sharply penetrated the sphere of culture, the humanitarian spheres of knowledge.

The concept of “technology” arose due to technical progress and, according to the dictionary interpretation (“techne” - art, craft, science; “logos” - concept, doctrine) means a set of knowledge about methods and means of processing materials. Technology also includes the art of knowing the process. The technological process always involves a certain sequence of operations with the use of the necessary tools and conditions. Technology, in a procedural sense, answers the question "how, with what, and with what means?"

In the 1920s, the term “pedagogical technology” was first mentioned in works on pedagogy. At the same time, another term, “pedagogical technique”, also spread. It was expressed in the pedagogical encyclopedia of the 1930s as methods and tools aimed at the precise and effective organization of educational activities. Pedagogical technologies also included skills in working with educational and laboratory equipment, and the use of visual aids.

In the mid-1960s, the content of this concept was widely discussed abroad in pedagogical publications and at international conferences, as a result of which two directions of its interpretation were determined in this area in different countries (USA, England, Japan, France, Italy, Hungary).

Supporters of the first direction emphasized the need to use technical means and programmed teaching aids (technology in education).

Supporters of the second direction considered it important to increase the efficiency of the organization of the educational process and eliminate the lag of

pedagogical ideas behind the rapid development of technology. Thus, the first direction was designated as “Technical means in teaching”, and the second direction, which arose a little later, was designated as “teaching technology” or “technology of the educational process”.

In the early 1970s, it was realized that there was a need to modernize various types of educational equipment and teaching aids. Without them, it was impossible to achieve high-quality and effective teaching. In the mid-1960s and early 1970s, magazines dealing with issues of pedagogical technologies began to be published in highly developed countries such as the USA, England, Japan, and Italy, and later specialized organizations and centers began to deal with this problem.

Educational technology centers in developed countries

In the USA, 1971 - the American Association for Educational Communications and Technology was founded. Currently, 50 branches of this council operate throughout the country and in Canada. In the USA, the journal Educational Technology began to be published in 1961, and in 1971 - the journal Audiovisual Teaching.

In England, 1967 - the National Council for Educational Technology began to publish the journal Educational Technology and Programming Learning in 1964, and in 1971 - the journal Educational Technology.

In Japan, 4 scientific organizations are engaged in the problems of pedagogical technologies. In 1967, the “National Council for Pedagogical Technologies” was established, its branches are located in 22 state universities. Since 1965, the journal “Pedagogical Technology” has been published quarterly in Japanese and the journal “Research in the Field of Pedagogical Technologies” in English twice a year. Recently, the “All-Japan Central Council for Pedagogical Technologies” has been established, which is also engaged in establishing international relations on problems.

In Italy, in 1971, the National Center for Pedagogical Technologies was established and the journal “Pedagogical Technologies” is published.

In Hungary - in 1973, the State Center for Educational Technology was established. At the International Seminar on Educational Technology (Budapest, 1977), scientist S.G. Shapovalenko outlined three technological principles of the educational process:

1. Perfect mastery of knowledge and techniques.
2. Familiarity with the fund of audiovisual materials.
3. Knowledge of the methodology for their effective use, including the development of a creative approach.

Hungarian scientist L. Salai significantly expanded the scope of the organizers of the educational process by including in the concept of "teaching technology" planning, analysis of goals, scientific organization of the educational process, selection of the most important tools and materials in order to increase its effectiveness. According to the data collected by E. Bisterski and J. Sellers (USA), teaching techniques are not only auxiliary tools and new systems, but also play a major role in its development, changing the organizational form, method and content of the educational process. This, in turn, had a great impact on the pedagogical thinking of teachers and students.

In the 1990s, the Center for Pedagogical Technologies was established in Russia, and the journals "School Technology" and "Innovations in Education" were published.

Since the adoption of the National Program for Personnel Training in Uzbekistan in 1997, the problems of pedagogical technologies have been raised as topical research objects in the education system and in pedagogical publications.

In 1999, the Center for Pedagogical Technologies was established under the Republican Center for Education. Journals such as “Educational Technologies”, “Educational Problems” began to be published, articles on the problems of

pedagogical technologies are published in the journals “Public Education”, “Pedagogical Education”, “Education and Training”, “Enlightenment”, “Teachers' Newspaper” and other scientific and pedagogical publications.

In 1994, the 1st Republican Scientific and Theoretical Conference on the Problems of Pedagogical Technologies was held, the materials of the lectures and reports were published in a special collection.

Pedagogical scientists U. Nishonaliyev, N.S. Saidakhmedov, N.N. Azizkhodjayeva, Ziyamukhammedov, U. Tolipov, B.L. Farberman and others are conducting serious research on the problems of pedagogical technologies in the Republic.

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